

Assessment of Postoperative Nausea and Vomiting: Prevention Strategies and Outcomes

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Abstract

Background: Postoperative nausea and vomiting (PONV) remain a significant challenge in surgical care. This study evaluated the efficacy of ondansetron and dexamethasone, alone and in combination, for PONV prophylaxis.

Methods: A prospective, randomized, controlled trial enrolled 300 adult patients undergoing elective surgery under general anesthesia. Patients were randomly allocated to four groups (n=75 each): control, ondansetron (4 mg), dexamethasone (4 mg), and combination (ondansetron 4 mg + dexamethasone 4 mg). Primary outcome was PONV incidence within 24 hours post-surgery.

Results: The combination group demonstrated significantly lower PONV incidence (8.0%) compared to ondansetron (14.7%), dexamethasone (17.3%), and control groups (29.3%) (P<0.001). Rescue antiemetic requirements were lowest in the combination group (4.0%) versus control (20.0%), ondansetron (8.0%), and dexamethasone (9.3%) groups (P<0.001). Patient satisfaction was highest in the combination group (median score: 5 [IQR: 4-5], P<0.001). Multivariate analysis identified female gender (OR: 2.12, P=0.001), PONV history (OR: 2.65, P<0.001), and prolonged surgery (OR: 1.24, P=0.005) as significant risk factors.

Conclusion: Combination prophylaxis with ondansetron and dexamethasone significantly reduces PONV incidence and rescue antiemetic requirements while improving patient satisfaction, without increasing complications.

Keywords: Postoperative nausea and vomiting; PONV; ondansetron; dexamethasone; antiemetic prophylaxis; risk factors; combination therapy; patient satisfaction; surgical complications; anesthesia.

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Introduction

Postoperative nausea and vomiting (PONV) is a common and distressing complication following surgical procedures under general anesthesia, affecting approximately 30% of surgical patients and up to 80% of high-risk patients.[1] PONV not only causes significant discomfort and dissatisfaction for patients, but can also lead to serious postoperative complications such as dehydration, electrolyte imbalances, aspiration pneumonia, wound dehiscence, and delayed recovery and discharge.[2,3] Moreover, PONV is associated with increased healthcare costs due to prolonged post-anesthesia care unit (PACU) stay, unexpected hospital admission, and additional medication requirements.[4]

The etiology of PONV is multifactorial and involves a complex interplay of patient-related, anesthesia-related, and surgery-related factors.[5] Patient-related risk factors include female gender, non-smoking status, history of PONV or motion sickness, and young age. Anesthesia-related factors include the use of volatile anesthetics, nitrous

oxide, and opioids. Surgery-related factors include the type and duration of surgery, with prolonged procedures and those involving the ear, nose, throat, breast, and gastrointestinal tract carrying a higher risk. [1,6]

Given the significant impact of PONV on patient outcomes and healthcare costs, effective prevention and management strategies are crucial. A multimodal approach incorporating both pharmacological and non-pharmacological interventions has been recommended by international guidelines.[7,8] Pharmacological prophylaxis with antiemetic medications, such as 5-HT₃ receptor antagonists (e.g., ondansetron), neurokinin-1 (NK-1) receptor antagonists (e.g., aprepitant), corticosteroids (e.g., dexamethasone), and dopamine receptor antagonists (e.g., droperidol), has been shown to significantly reduce the incidence and severity of PONV.[9] However, the choice of antiemetic agents should be individualized based on the patient's risk factors, potential side effects, and cost-effectiveness.[10]

Non-pharmacological interventions, such as acupuncture, acupressure, and aromatherapy, have also demonstrated efficacy in preventing PONV.[11] Acupuncture at the P6 (Neiguan) point has been found to reduce the incidence of PONV compared to sham acupuncture or no treatment.[12] Similarly, acupressure wristbands that stimulate the P6 point have shown promising results in reducing PONV, especially in combination with antiemetic medications.[13] Aromatherapy with essential oils, such as peppermint, ginger, and lavender, has also been reported to alleviate PONV symptoms, although the evidence is less robust compared to acupuncture and acupressure.[14]

In addition to prophylactic measures, the management of established PONV is equally important. A stepwise approach based on the severity of symptoms and response to initial treatment is recommended.[7] Mild PONV can often be managed with conservative measures such as hydration, oxygen therapy, and antiemetic medications. In contrast, severe or refractory PONV may require more aggressive interventions, such as combination antiemetic therapy, intravenous fluids, and in rare cases, nasogastric decompression.[15]

To optimize PONV prevention and management, a systematic and standardized approach to patient assessment and risk stratification is essential. Several risk scoring systems, such as the Apfel score and the Koivuranta score, have been developed to predict the likelihood of PONV based on patient-related and anesthesia-related factors. [16,17] These scoring systems can help identify high-risk patients who may benefit from more aggressive prophylaxis and closer monitoring. Additionally, the use of PONV-specific quality improvement initiatives, such as standardized protocols, order sets, and educational programs, has been shown to improve adherence to evidence-based guidelines and reduce the incidence of PONV. [18,19]

Despite the availability of effective prevention and management strategies, PONV remains a significant challenge in clinical practice. This is partly due to the variability in individual patient responses to antiemetic medications and the lack of a universally effective single intervention.[20] Furthermore, the occurrence of PONV can be influenced by factors beyond the control of healthcare providers, such as the patient's genetic predisposition and the inherent emetogenic potential of certain surgical procedures.[21]

In conclusion, PONV is a common and potentially serious complication following surgery that can significantly impact patient outcomes and healthcare costs. A multimodal approach incorporating pharmacological and non-

pharmacological interventions, guided by patient risk stratification and evidence-based guidelines, is essential for effective prevention and management. Ongoing research is needed to further elucidate the underlying mechanisms of PONV, identify novel therapeutic targets, and develop more effective and personalized prevention strategies. By prioritizing PONV assessment and prevention, healthcare providers can improve patient satisfaction, reduce postoperative complications, and optimize resource utilization in the surgical setting.

Aims and Objectives

The primary aim of this study was to assess the effectiveness of various prevention strategies for postoperative nausea and vomiting (PONV) and their impact on patient outcomes. The specific objectives were to evaluate the incidence of PONV in patients undergoing surgical procedures under general anesthesia, identify risk factors associated with the development of PONV, compare the efficacy of pharmacological and non-pharmacological interventions in reducing PONV, and assess the impact of PONV on patient satisfaction, postoperative complications, and healthcare costs.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Setting: A prospective, randomized, controlled trial was conducted between September 2020 and February 2022 at Karpagam Faculty of Medical Sciences and Research, Othakalmandapam, Coimbatore. The study protocol was approved by the institutional review board, and written informed consent was obtained from all participants.

Study Population: Adult patients (aged 18 years or older) scheduled to undergo elective surgical procedures under general anesthesia were eligible for inclusion in the study. Patients were excluded if they had a history of allergies to any of the study medications, severe hepatic or renal impairment, a body mass index greater than 40 kg/m², or if they were pregnant or breastfeeding. Additionally, patients who had received antiemetic medications within 24 hours before surgery or had a history of alcohol or drug abuse were also excluded.

Sample Size and Randomization: The sample size was calculated based on an expected PONV incidence of 30% in the control group and a desired reduction of 50% in the intervention groups, with a power of 80% and an alpha level of 0.05. A total of 300 patients were enrolled and randomly allocated to one of four groups (75 patients per group) using a computer-generated randomization sequence:

1. Control group receiving no prophylaxis
2. Ondansetron group receiving 4 mg intravenous (IV) ondansetron before the end of surgery

3. Dexamethasone group receiving 4 mg IV dexamethasone before induction of anesthesia
4. Combination group receiving both ondansetron (4 mg) and dexamethasone (4 mg)

The randomization sequence was generated using block randomization with a block size of four to ensure equal distribution among groups. Group assignments were sealed in sequentially numbered, opaque envelopes that were opened only after patient enrolment.

Anesthesia and Postoperative Management: All patients underwent a standardized general anesthesia protocol, which included propofol for induction, sevoflurane for maintenance, and fentanyl for intraoperative analgesia. Postoperative pain management consisted of IV patient-controlled analgesia with morphine or hydromorphone. Rescue antiemetic medication (10 mg IV metoclopramide) was administered if patients experienced two or more episodes of PONV or at their request.

Data Collection and Outcome Measures: Demographic and clinical data, including age, gender, body mass index, smoking status, history of PONV or motion sickness, type and duration of surgery, and postoperative opioid consumption, were collected. The primary outcome measure was the incidence of PONV within the first 24 hours after surgery. Secondary outcomes included the severity of PONV (assessed using a visual analog scale), the need for rescue antiemetic medication, patient satisfaction (assessed using a 5-point Likert scale), and the incidence of postoperative complications (e.g., dehydration, electrolyte imbalances, aspiration pneumonia, and wound dehiscence).

All assessments were performed by trained research nurses who were blinded to the group allocation. PONV severity was assessed using a visual analog scale ranging from 0 (no nausea) to 10 (worst possible nausea). Patient satisfaction was evaluated using a 5-point Likert scale (1 = very dissatisfied, 5 = very satisfied) at 24 hours postoperatively.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 26.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA). Continuous variables were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation or median (interquartile range), while categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages. The incidence of PONV and postoperative complications were compared among the four groups using the chi-square test or Fisher's exact test, as appropriate. The severity of PONV and patient satisfaction scores were compared using the Kruskal-Wallis test, followed by pairwise comparisons with the Mann-Whitney U test. A post-hoc power analysis was conducted to confirm the adequacy of the

sample size. A P-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant. To account for multiple comparisons, the Bonferroni correction was applied where appropriate.

Results

Demographic and Clinical Characteristics: The study included 300 patients equally distributed across four groups (75 patients per group). Analysis of demographic data revealed comparable characteristics across all groups. The mean age of patients ranged from 44.8 ± 11.9 years in the ondansetron group to 45.6 ± 12.1 years in the dexamethasone group, showing no significant difference between groups ($P=0.948$). Female participants constituted the majority in all groups, with proportions ranging from 62.7% in the dexamethasone group to 68.0% in the ondansetron group ($P=0.833$). Body mass index measurements were consistent across groups, ranging from 26.2 ± 4.1 kg/m² in the dexamethasone group to 26.8 ± 4.5 kg/m² in the ondansetron group ($P=0.684$). The proportion of smokers was similar across groups, varying from 14.7% in the dexamethasone group to 18.7% in the ondansetron group ($P=0.814$).

Incidence of PONV: Statistical analysis demonstrated significant differences in PONV incidence among the four groups ($P<0.001$). The control group exhibited the highest incidence at 29.3% (22 patients), followed by the dexamethasone group at 17.3% (13 patients), and the ondansetron group at 14.7% (11 patients). The combination therapy group showed the lowest incidence at 8.0% (6 patients), representing a significant reduction compared to all other groups.

Severity of PONV and Rescue Antiemetic Requirements: The severity of PONV, assessed using median scores with interquartile ranges (IQR), showed significant variation among groups ($P<0.001$). The control group reported the highest severity with a median score of 3 (IQR: 2-5), while the combination group demonstrated the lowest severity with a median score of 1 (IQR: 0-2). Both ondansetron and dexamethasone monotherapy groups showed intermediate severity scores of 2, with IQRs of 1-3 and 1-4, respectively.

The requirement for rescue antiemetic medication similarly showed significant differences between groups ($P<0.001$). The highest requirement was observed in the control group (20.0%, 15 patients), followed by the dexamethasone group (9.3%, 7 patients), and the ondansetron group (8.0%, 6 patients). The combination therapy group showed the lowest requirement at 4.0% (3 patients).

Patient Satisfaction: Patient satisfaction scores demonstrated significant differences among groups ($P<0.001$). The combination therapy group achieved the highest median satisfaction score of 5

(IQR: 4-5). Both ondansetron and dexamethasone groups showed median scores of 4, with IQRs of 3-5 and 3-4, respectively. The control group reported the lowest satisfaction with a median score of 3 (IQR: 2-4).

Postoperative Complications: Analysis of postoperative complications revealed no statistically significant differences among groups. Dehydration rates ranged from 5.3% (4 patients) in the control group to 1.3% (1 patient) in the combination group (P=0.241). Electrolyte imbalance occurred in 4.0% (3 patients) of control group patients compared to 1.3% (1 patient) in the combination group (P=0.261). Aspiration pneumonia was observed in 1.3% (1 patient) of patients in all groups except the combination group, where no cases were reported (P=0.564). Wound dehiscence rates were comparable across groups, affecting 2.7% (2 patients) in the control group and

1.3% (1 patient) in each of the treatment groups (P=0.560).

Risk Factor Analysis: Multivariate analysis identified several significant independent risk factors for PONV. Female gender showed an adjusted odds ratio (OR) of 2.12 (95% CI: 1.35-3.33, P=0.001). A history of PONV or motion sickness demonstrated the strongest association with an adjusted OR of 2.65 (95% CI: 1.64-4.29, P<0.001). Duration of surgery was also significant, with each hour increase associated with an adjusted OR of 1.24 (95% CI: 1.07-1.44, P=0.005). Postoperative opioid consumption showed a modest but significant effect, with an adjusted OR of 1.05 per mg increase (95% CI: 1.01-1.09, P=0.011). While smoking status showed significance in univariate analysis (OR: 0.56, 95% CI: 0.32-0.99, P=0.045), this effect was not maintained in the multivariate model (adjusted OR: 0.61, 95% CI: 0.34-1.09, P=0.097).

Table 1: Demographic and clinical characteristics of the study population

Characteristic	Control (n=75)	Ondansetron (n=75)	Dexamethasone (n=75)	Combination (n=75)	P-value
Age (years), mean \pm SD	45.2 \pm 12.3	44.8 \pm 11.9	45.6 \pm 12.1	45.1 \pm 12.0	0.948
Female, n (%)	49 (65.3)	51 (68.0)	47 (62.7)	50 (66.7)	0.833
BMI (kg/m ²), mean \pm SD	26.4 \pm 4.2	26.8 \pm 4.5	26.2 \pm 4.1	26.6 \pm 4.3	0.684
Smoking status, n (%)	12 (16.0)	14 (18.7)	11 (14.7)	12 (16.0)	0.814

Table 2: Incidence of PONV within the first 24 hours after surgery

Group	Incidence of PONV, n (%)	P-value
Control	22 (29.3)	<0.001
Ondansetron	11 (14.7)	
Dexamethasone	13 (17.3)	
Combination	6 (8.0)	

Table 3: Severity of PONV and need for rescue antiemetic medication

Group	PONV severity, median (IQR)	P-value	Rescue antiemetic, n (%)	P-value
Control	3 (2-5)	<0.001	15 (20.0)	<0.001
Ondansetron	2 (1-3)		6 (8.0)	
Dexamethasone	2 (1-4)		7 (9.3)	
Combination	1 (0-2)		3 (4.0)	

Table 4: Patient satisfaction scores

Group	Patient satisfaction, median (IQR)	P-value
Control	3 (2-4)	<0.001
Ondansetron	4 (3-5)	
Dexamethasone	4 (3-4)	
Combination	5 (4-5)	

Table 5: Incidence of postoperative complications

Complication	Control, n (%)	Ondansetron, n (%)	Dexamethasone, n (%)	Combination, n (%)	P-value
Dehydration	4 (5.3)	2 (2.7)	2 (2.7)	1 (1.3)	0.241
Electrolyte imbalance	3 (4.0)	2 (2.7)	2 (2.7)	1 (1.3)	0.261
Aspiration pneumonia	1 (1.3)	1 (1.3)	1 (1.3)	0 (0.0)	0.564
Wound dehiscence	2 (2.7)	1 (1.3)	1 (1.3)	1 (1.3)	0.560

Table 6: Univariate and multivariate analyses of risk factors for PONV

	Univariate analysis		Multivariate analysis	
	OR (95% CI)	P-value	OR (95% CI)	P-value
Age (per year increase)	0.99 (0.97-1.01)	0.288	-	-
Female gender	2.24 (1.45-3.46)	<0.001	2.12 (1.35-3.33)	0.001
BMI (per kg/m ² increase)	1.03 (0.98-1.08)	0.288	-	-
Smoking status	0.56 (0.32-0.99)	0.045	0.61 (0.34-1.09)	0.097
History of PONV or motion sickness	2.81 (1.76-4.48)	<0.001	2.65 (1.64-4.29)	<0.001
Duration of surgery (per hour increase)	1.28 (1.11-1.48)	0.001	1.24 (1.07-1.44)	0.005
Postoperative opioid consumption (per mg increase)	1.06 (1.02-1.10)	0.002	1.05 (1.01-1.09)	0.011

Discussion

The present study examined the efficacy of different antiemetic regimens for PONV prophylaxis, demonstrating that the combination of ondansetron 4 mg and dexamethasone 4 mg provides superior prophylaxis compared to either agent alone or no prophylaxis. The combination therapy resulted in significantly lower PONV incidence (8.0%) compared to ondansetron (14.7%), dexamethasone (17.3%), and control groups (29.3%) ($P<0.001$).

These findings are consistent with the meta-analysis by Habib et al. [11], who analyzed 17 randomized controlled trials involving 1,462 patients. They reported that combination therapy reduced PONV incidence by 43% compared to ondansetron alone (RR: 0.57, 95% CI: 0.45-0.72, $P<0.001$) and by 38% compared to dexamethasone alone (RR: 0.62, 95% CI: 0.49-0.78, $P<0.001$). Similarly, Wu et al. [12] demonstrated in their systematic review of 14 studies ($n=1,968$) that the combination reduced relative risk by 52% compared to monotherapy (RR: 0.48, 95% CI: 0.37-0.63, $P<0.001$).

However, some studies have reported contrasting results. The randomized controlled trial by Thompson et al. [13] involving 320 patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy found no significant difference between combination therapy (12.5%) and ondansetron monotherapy (15.6%, $P=0.42$). These disparate findings might be attributed to var

iations in surgical procedures, timing of antiemetic administration, and different patient populations.

Risk factor analysis in our study identified female gender (OR: 2.12, $P=0.001$), history of PONV or motion sickness (OR: 2.65, $P<0.001$), and duration of surgery (OR: 1.24, $P=0.005$) as significant pre

dictors of PONV. These findings align with the large-scale multicenter study by Nakamura et al. [14], which analyzed 21,606 surgical cases and reported similar risk factors: female gender (OR: 2.31, 95% CI: 2.09-2.56), history of PONV (OR:

2.73, 95% CI: 2.44-3.07), and prolonged surgery (OR: 1.31 per hour, 95% CI: 1.22-1.40).

The significantly reduced need for rescue antiemetics in the combination group (4.0%) compared to monotherapy groups (ondansetron: 8.0%, dexamethasone: 9.3%) supports the findings of Yoshida et al. [15]. Their prospective study of 428 patients showed rescue antiemetic requirements of 5.2% with combination therapy versus 11.8% with ondansetron alone ($P<0.001$).

Patient satisfaction scores were notably higher in the combination group (median: 5, IQR: 4-5) compared to other groups ($P<0.001$). This corresponds with the findings of Lee et al. [16], who reported significantly higher satisfaction scores with combination therapy (4.5 ± 0.6) compared to monotherapy (3.8 ± 0.8 , $P<0.001$) in their study of 375 patients.

The safety profile analysis revealed no significant increase in complications with combination therapy, consistent with the comprehensive safety review by Matsumoto et al. [17] of 2,478 patients receiving various antiemetic combinations. They reported no significant differences in adverse events between combination therapy and monotherapy groups (complication rates: 3.2% vs. 2.9%, $P=0.68$).

Conclusion

This randomized controlled trial provides robust evidence supporting the superior efficacy of combination antiemetic prophylaxis using ondansetron 4 mg and dexamethasone 4 mg for preventing PONV. The combination therapy demonstrated significant advantages over monotherapy, reducing PONV incidence to 8.0% compared to 14.7% with ondansetron alone and 17.3% with dexamethasone alone. This enhanced efficacy was achieved without increasing adverse events, suggesting a favorable risk-benefit profile.

The study also confirmed established risk factors for PONV, including female gender, history of PONV or motion sickness, extended surgical duration, and postoperative opioid consumption. This risk factor identification enables targeted

prophylaxis for high-risk patients, potentially improving resource utilization and patient outcomes.

The significantly higher patient satisfaction scores and reduced need for rescue antiemetics in the combination therapy group suggest that this approach not only prevents PONV more effectively but also enhances the overall quality of postoperative care. These findings support the implementation of combination prophylaxis as a standard protocol, particularly for patients with multiple risk factors.

Future research should focus on developing personalized prophylaxis strategies based on individual risk profiles and investigating the cost-effectiveness of routine combination therapy compared to risk-stratified approaches

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